

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ART OF MUSIC

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Abstract. *In this article, it is said that music teaches to understand and see beauty and ugliness, high and low, joy and sadness, and aesthetic education serves to establish universal and national values.*

Key words: *music, art, aesthetic education, emotional feelings, pedagogues.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация. *В данной статье говорится, что музыка учит понимать и видеть красоту и уродство, высокое и низкое, радость и печаль, а эстетическое воспитание служит утверждению общечеловеческих и национальных ценностей.*

Ключевые слова: *музыка, искусство, эстетическое воспитание, эмоциональные переживания, педагоги.*

Music is such an art form that unites people through their experiences and emotional feelings. It becomes a means of communication between them. It can be called a miracle that the music created by one composer evokes different experiences in the hearts of other people. Music education is a component of aesthetic education. One of the leading factors shaping human personality is education. Aesthetic education is based on the doctrine of the essence of beauty, the unity of aesthetic and moral feelings, the nationalism of art as its component, expands and deepens children's knowledge of the objective world, develops creative ability and talent. and helps them to develop high spiritual qualities. It is usually understood that the goal of aesthetic education is to develop aesthetic feelings and thoughts in children, to be able to see and enjoy beauty.

In fact, the goals and tasks of aesthetic education are not limited to this, it teaches children to understand and see beauty and ugliness, high and low, joy and sadness. Aesthetic education serves to establish universal and national values. It is clear that education affects a person's mind, feelings, imagination, beliefs, outlook, actions, and behavior.

The language of music is understandable and close to everyone. That is why the music of all nations is attractive.

Music reflects thoughts and feelings through sounds, and describes the moral problems that have affected humanity in the stages of life. Philosophical essence of music is also revealed in this.

Great musical works are imbued with deep philosophical content, music reflects issues such as life and death, individual and society, goodness and oppression, power and weakness.

Musicologists, thinkers and scientists have long been interested in the infinite possibilities of music's influence on the human psyche. Philosophers, psychologists, pedagogues and public figures have tried to determine the features of music that influence the formation of a person as a person. Since ancient times, there have been ideas about the influence of music, especially its components - rhythm and melody, on human mood, changing his inner world.

The art of music, as an important factor of aesthetic education, has a strong influence on personality formation. Proper organization of music lessons in the family, in the MTM, at school is an effective way to enrich the inner world of the young generation and to understand art correctly. Music expresses human feelings, hopes, and desires in its own artistic language and has an active influence on human emotions. Music is both science and art. It is based on physics and mathematics, which make music a science. But you can't look at a piece of music as a static concept of this science. Because music is a living art that is always developing. The art of music becomes a companion of a person from the first years of his life and makes a significant contribution to the general cultural development. Music is a constant companion of human life. According to Stendhal, music is one of the forms of art that can penetrate deep into the heart of a person and reflect his inner experiences. "Music belongs to the system of expressive art. Music also expresses events. But it is not determined by the dimensions of space and material objects, as in architecture. Music is not perceived by sight, but by hearing. Since the theme of music has acquired its own characteristics and cannot cover all aspects of a person and reality, it primarily expresses the inner spiritual world of a person, his feelings and mood... music creates an emotional image of reality. » Music has a wide range of mood expressions. Human mood is a complex emotion that is not connected to anything. Mood acquires a generalized character, secondary aspects are excluded from it, and the most important aspects that determine the emotional attitude of a person to reality are isolated. The power of music is that it can show happiness, sadness, fantasy, endurance, courage, depression and similar human mental states in a private and general way, in their interdependence, in their absorption into each other. The "language" of music expresses the unity of all parts, the form of the work. Form is a material expression of musical content. The composer's thoughts, feelings, and imagination reach the listeners through the musical form. Therefore, it opens a wide way to master the "language" of music, to understand its essence, to master the wealth of thoughts, feelings, and experiences in music. Ancient thinkers emphasized the importance of musical education for the growing generation.

The human and positive qualities of a future member of society are formed right from childhood. It was during this period that music was considered a means of forming positive qualities. Music is created in singing and dancing, and later becomes an independent type of artistic creation, it acquires a unique artistic expression "language", specially designed and selected sounds are the source of this "language".

Of course, music does not determine the directions of personality formation and its positive qualities by itself. The most important aspects of the educational effect depend on the ideological content of the musical work. Thus, the tasks of musical-aesthetic education are determined. The famous Polish composer K. Szymanowski in his article entitled "Educational value of music in society", speaking about the natural power of music - that it can be used in two opposite directions - to create and destroy - "directing it to the necessary work, "It is necessary to use the power of music effectively, just like using the waters of a fast-flowing river for useful and productive work, i.e. to turn a mill." The effect of music on a person, its place in the spiritual life of an individual and society is a complex problem. This complexity and sophistication did not come to science immediately. At this point, it is appropriate to remember the words of Asafev: "...music is both art, science, language, and game."

So, in the formation of aesthetic, musical and personal characteristics of children the role of music is incomparable. Music affects a person in every way: the melody and its musical expression have a deep impact on a person's emotions, evoke different feelings and create different moods. The text and ideological content of the song affects not only the emotions, but also the minds of the listeners, excites them and forces them to think. It arouses in people a certain attitude towards the spiritual problems reflected in the work. Such influence is very complex and powerful.

REFERENCES

1. Qoshiyeva J. B. History of Uzbek folk Music //American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750). – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 8. – С. 108-110.
2. Jaqsimuratova B. FORMATION OF SINGING SKILLS IN PRIMARY GRADES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – С. 281-288.
3. Jaqsimuratova B. FORMATION OF SINGING SKILLS IN PRIMARY GRADES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – С. 281-288.
4. Бағдагул Ж. ҚОРАҚАЛПОҚ ВОКАЛІ САНЪАТИНИНГ АСОСЧИСИ БАЗАРБАЙ НАДИРОВ. – 2023.

5. Abatbayeva U. INITIAL LEVEL OF STUDENTS'MUSICAL CREATIVITY DEVELOPMENT //Modern Science And Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 323-326.
6. Абатбаева У. А. Арт-Педагогические И Арт-Терапевтические Технологии, Методы Пребывания В Образовании, Формы И Инструменты //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – Т. 40. – С. 496-498.
7. Abatbayeva U. INITIAL LEVEL OF STUDENTS'MUSICAL CREATIVITY DEVELOPMENT //Modern Science And Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 323-326.
8. Абатбаева У. А. Арт-Педагогические И Арт-Терапевтические Технологии, Методы Пребывания В Образовании, Формы И Инструменты //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – Т. 40. – С. 496-498.
9. Allambergenovna A. R. THE MANIFESTATION OF EUROPEAN AND NATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE OPERA " GULAYIM" //International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 185-187.
10. Абатбаева Р. А. ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОН МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИДА МАШХУР БАСТАТОР Н. МУҲАММЕДДИНОВНИНГ ЎРНИ //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 648-653.
11. АБАТБАЕВА Р. КОМПОЗИТОР НАЖИМАДДИН МУХАММЕДДИНОВ ИЖОДИДА ТАРИХИЙ СИЙМОЛАР //Journal of Culture and Art. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-66.
12. Tajimuratova S. CONCEPT OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 251-254.
13. Tajimuratova S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 841-849.
14. Saginbaevna T. S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 9. – С. 386-392.
15. Sag'inbaevna T. S. Cultural Life in Uzbekistan during the Years of Independence //Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. – 2023. – Т. 18. – С. 39-41.
16. Tajimuratova S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 841-849.

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ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYASI

17. Saginbaevna T. S. Management and study of culture and art. – 2022.
18. Тажимуратова Ш. С. САНЪАТШУНОСЛИК ФАНЛАРИНИ ЎҚИТИШ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ИШЛАШ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. – 2023.
19. Tajimuraova S. S. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS IN MANAGEMENT //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 509-511.

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